

Implementation of Contextualize School Guidance Activities and Values Formation of Intermediate Learners

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Abstract. This study determined domains of contextualized school guidance activities which significantly influenced values formation of intermediate learners. This study used the descriptive correlational design quantitative research design. The respondents of this study were composed of 79 students in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur using the Tabachnick Fidell Formula. The data analysis utilized the mean, Pearson r, and regression analysis. The findings revealed that the implementation of contextualized school guidance activities in terms of academic development, career development, and personal and social development was consistently manifested. Moreover, values formation in terms of courtesy rules, friendship, family relationships, rules of conduct in social environments, effective usage of time, health and blessings, avoidance of violence, and healthy living was also consistently observed. Furthermore, the study found a strong positive relationship between the implementation of contextualized school guidance activities and values formation, indicating that well-structured guidance programs contribute significantly to the development of positive values among learners. It revealed further that while certain aspects of contextualized school guidance activities are important, personal and social development stands out as the most influential factor in shaping intermediate learners' values formation. Based on the findings, the teachers should actively integrate values education into their teaching strategies by modeling positive behaviors, encouraging respectful interactions, and providing structured opportunities for students to develop conflict resolution skills.

KEY WORDS

1. School guidance activities
2. values formation
3. personal and social development
4. intermediate learners

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1. Introduction

Academic institutions across the global context face a critical challenge in the prevalence of undesirable attitudes among learners in the classroom. Student misbehaviors and undesirable attitudes in the classroom have significantly impacted both the social and academic aspects of education. According to a study by the OECD in 2019, 29

Locally, there is a lack of studies administered in the Davao Region about the effectiveness, problems, and student-teacher perception regarding the relationship between contextualized guidance activities and values formation of intermediate learners. However, elementary teachers, particularly in the Division of Davao del Sur, Padada Central Elementary schools,

express their various observations of the prevalence of disruptive behaviors among students, negatively impacting their relationships with peers, family, and teachers and adversely affecting their academic performance and personal development.

With this, the researcher will investigate the extent of contextualized school guidance activities and the level of value formation of intermediate learners in Padada Central Elementary School, Padada, Davao del Sur. This is conducted to address the root causes of negative classroom behavior and attitudes, and assess the effectiveness of contextualized school guidance activities in terms of fostering values formation among intermediate learners. This is also carried out to examine the relationship between guidance activities, and learners' value development to provide enhanced school guidance programs and activities in equipping students with social, emotional, and ethical skills necessary to foster positive classroom environments and their holistic development.

The aforementioned statements underscore the critical need to study implementation of contextualized school guidance activities and the values formation of intermediate learners. In light of the foregoing, the researcher is motivated to pursue this study because it is critical to determine which domains of contextualized school guidance activities that significantly influence values formation of intermediate learners. Numerous studies have explored values formation of learners, but little to no extent was the implementation of contextualized guidance activities were tackled. Hence, the results of this study may provide information on how implementation of contextualized guidance activities significantly influence the values formation of intermediate learners in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur.

The specific objectives of the study are the following: a.) to determine the extent of the implementation of contextualized school guidance

activities in terms of academic development, career development, and social personal development. b.) to determine the extent of values formation of intermediate learners in terms of courtesy rules, friendship, being family, rules of conduct in social environments, effective usage of time, health and blessings, avoiding violence, and healthy living. c.) to determine if there is a significant relationship between the extent of the implementation of contextualized school guidance activities and extent of values formation of intermediate learners, and d.) to determine which domains of contextualized school guidance activities significantly influence values formation of intermediate learners.

At .05 level of significance, the following hypothesis was tested: a.) There is no significant relationship between the extent of the implementation of contextualized school guidance activities and extent of values formation of intermediate learners. b.) None of the domains of contextualized school guidance activities significantly influence values formation of intermediate learners.

The study will benefit various stakeholders. The Department of Education may use the study's findings to develop policies that contextualize school guidance activities as key to shaping students into value-driven individuals. School heads can use the results to design programs that strengthen students' moral development, while teachers gain insights into integrating life skills and values into instruction for holistic growth. Students benefit from understanding how guidance activities support academic success and ethical behavior, fostering responsibility and empathy.

Figure 1 illustrated the conceptual framework delineating the study's variables. The study identified the contextualized school guidance activities as the independent variable, assessed through academic development, career development, and social personal development. Meanwhile, the dependent variable of the study

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

was the values formation of learners, assessed through courtesy rules, friendship, being family, rules of conduct in social environments, effective usage of time, health, and blessings, avoid-

ing of violence, and healthy living. Furthermore, the study sought to determine the relationship between the two variables.

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a quantitative descriptive-correlational design to explore the extent of contextualized school guidance activities and their relationship with values formation among intermediate learners. This design allowed for the systematic description of current practices and the analysis of associations between key variables without implying causation (Creswell Creswell, 2023). The descriptive part focused on academic, career, and social-personal development, while also assessing values like courtesy, friendship, time management, and non-violence (McCombes, 2023). The correlational aspect examined whether higher implementation of guidance activities is linked to stronger values formation, using real-world educational data (Cherry, 2023). Though causality was not determined, the findings offer insights that can guide improvements in school guidance programs and support students’ holistic development (Fraenkel, Wallen, Hyun, 2022).

research integrity. Key ethical considerations included informed consent, confidentiality, participant safety, and transparency. The study aimed to improve school guidance programs and values formation for learners, benefiting DepEd, school heads, teachers, students, and future researchers. Informed consent was obtained from school authorities and parents, with participants assured of voluntary participation and confidentiality. The researcher was qualified, had adequate resources, and ensured fairness and objectivity throughout the study. Data was securely stored, and ethical standards were upheld, ensuring transparency and respect for participants.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The researcher followed RMC’s Research Ethics guidelines, ensuring participant protection and

2.3. Research Respondents—The study targeted intermediate learners in the Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur, with a final sample size of 79, based on Tabachnick and Fidell’s (2007) formula and adjusted for data retrieval issues. It examined the influence of three sub-variables—academic, career, and social-personal development—on values formation, including courtesy, friendship, family re-

relationships, social conduct, time management, health, and non-violence. Universal sampling was used when possible, covering all eligible Grade 4 to 6 learners exposed to contextualized school guidance activities. Clear inclusion and exclusion criteria ensured the relevance and accuracy of the data, providing meaningful insights into how these activities contribute to values development.

2.4. Research Instrument—This study used two researcher-made questionnaires validated by experts and tested for reliability through a pilot study conducted in a school outside the research area. The instruments, focused

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The study followed a systematic and ethical data gathering process. After securing approvals from the RMC Ethics Review Board, Dean of Graduate Studies, and the Schools Division Superintendent, formal letters were sent to school principals. Parental consent and student assent were obtained, with all participants fully

2.6. Data Analysis—The study used several statistical tools to analyze the relationship between contextualized school guidance activities and values formation. The mean was employed to assess the levels of guidance activities and values formation. Pearson r was used

on assessing the implementation of contextualized school guidance activities and learners' values formation, showed high reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of .891. The section on guidance activities covered academic, career, and social-personal development, aligned with existing student support systems to address learners' academic and emotional needs. The values formation section measured indicators such as courtesy, friendship, family relationships, social conduct, time management, health, and non-violence, offering insights into the impact of guidance interventions on students' personal growth and well-being.

briefed. The researcher-made questionnaire was validated by experts and pilot-tested with 30 non-participant teachers to ensure reliability. Surveys were administered face-to-face in three Padada District schools, with immediate retrieval and review to ensure completeness. Data were analyzed using SPSS to examine the relationship between contextualized guidance activities and learners' values formation.

to determine the strength and significance of the relationship between the implementation of guidance activities and values formation. Additionally, multiple linear regression was applied to identify which domains of guidance activities significantly influenced students' values formation.

3. Results and Discussion

This part presented the results of the study. The presentation proceeded with a comprehensive discussion of implementation of contextualized school guidance activities. The chapter subsequently provided the analysis of values formation of intermediate learners. This was followed by a discussion about the correlation between the two variables. The concluding part addressed the domains of contextualized school guidance activities which significantly influenced values formation of intermediate learners.

3.1. *Extent of Implementation of Contextualized School Guidance Activities*—Table 1 presented a summary of the extent of implementation of contextualized school guidance activities. These were evaluated in terms of academic development, career development, and social personal development. The mean scores for each indicator were interpreted as follows: Academic Development (4.24), marked as very extensive; Career Development (4.25), marked as very extensive; social personal development

(4.24), marked as very extensive. The findings demonstrated an overall mean rating of (4.24) marked as Very Extensive. This highlighted that the implementation of contextualized school guidance activities was always manifested. Of the indicators, career development received the greatest mean rating of 4.25, categorized as very extensive, whilst both academic development as well as social personal development recorded the lowest mean rating of 4.24, categorized also as very extensive.

Table 1. Extent of Implementation of Contextualized School Guidance Activities

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Academic Development	4.24	Very Extensive
2	Career Development	4.25	Very Extensive
3	Social Personal Development	4.24	Very Extensive
	Overall	4.24	Very Extensive

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79: Not Extensive, 1.80 – 2.59: Less Extensive, 2.60 – 3.39: Moderately Extensive, 3.40 – 4.19: Extensive, 4.20 – 5.00: Very Extensive

3.2. *Extent of Values Formation of Intermediate Learners*—Table 2 presented a summary of the extent of values formation of intermediate learners. These were evaluated in terms of courtesy rules, friendship, being family, rules of conduct in social environments, effective usage of time, health and blessings, avoiding violence, and healthy living. The mean scores for each indicator were interpreted as follows: Courtesy Rules (4.31), marked as very extensive; Friendship (4.32) marked as very extensive; Being Family (4.29), marked as very extensive; Rules of Conduct in Social Environments (4.23), marked as very extensive; Effec-

tive Usage of Time, Health and Blessings (4.26), marked as very extensive; Avoiding Violence (4.23), marked as Very High; Healthy Living (4.41), marked as very extensive. The findings demonstrated an overall mean rating of (4.29), marked as Very Extensive. This highlighted that the values formation of intermediate learners was always manifested. Of the indicators, Healthy Living received the greatest mean rating of 4.41, categorized as very extensive, whilst Rules of Conduct in Social Environments as well as Avoiding Violence recorded the lowest mean rating of 4.23, also categorized as very extensive.

3.3. *Significant Relationship between Implementation of Contextualized School Guidance Activities and Values Formation of Intermediate Learners*—Table 3 flaunted the data on

the significant relationship between implementation of contextualized school guidance activities and values formation of intermediate learners in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur. The

Table 2. Extent of Values Formation of Intermediate Learners

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Courtesy Rules	4.31	Very Extensive
2	Friendship	4.32	Very Extensive
3	Being Family	4.29	Very Extensive
4	Rules of Conduct in Social Environments	4.23	Very Extensive
5	Effective Usage of Time, Health and Blessings	4.26	Very Extensive
6	Avoiding Violence	4.23	Very Extensive
7	Healthy Living	4.41	Very Extensive
	Overall	4.29	Very Extensive

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79: Not Extensive, 1.80 – 2.59: Less Extensive, 2.60 – 3.39: Moderately Extensive, 3.40 – 4.19: Extensive, 4.20 – 5.00: Very Extensive

Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r) was applied for the two (2) variables on their significant relationship. The results appeared a computed p-value of .000 which was lower than the .05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected since the value denotes of having a significant relationship.

Furthermore, the computed r-value of 0.75 denotes the correlation between the two variables with which the hypothesis on significant

relationship was tested. Clearly, the findings inferred a strong significant relationship between the Implementation of contextualized school guidance activities and values formation of intermediate learners in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur. Consequently, it is anticipated that improving contextualized school guidance activities will enhance values formation of intermediate learners, thereby positively influencing the overall classroom learning atmosphere.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Implementation of Contextualized School Guidance Activities and Values Formation of Intermediate Learners

Variables	r-value	Statistical Description	p-value	Decision
Implementation of Contextualized School Guidance Activities (x)	0.75	Strong Positive correlation	.000	Reject Ho
Values Formation (y)				

3.4. Domains of Implementation of Contextualized School Guidance Activities that significantly Influence Values Formation of Intermediate Learners—Table 4 exemplified the re-

gression test among implementation of contextualized school guidance activities namely: academic development, career development, and social personal development towards values formation of intermediate learners. The findings indicate a very strong significant relationship between the implementation of contextualized school guidance activities and values formation of intermediate learners. The analysis shows

an F-value of 42.725 with a p-value of $.000$, indicating a statistically significant model fit. Additionally, the R^2 value of $.5625$ suggests that 56.25 percent of the variance in values formation of intermediate learners is explained by the predictors, with the remaining variance attributed to factors not accounted for by the three dimensions under study.

Domains of Implementation of Contextualized School Guidance Activities that Significantly Influence Values Formation of Intermediate Learners

Implementation of Contextualized School Guidance Activities	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
Constant	0.864	0.313		2.757	0.007	Reject Ho
Academic Development	-0.006	0.194	-0.006	-0.029	0.977	Accept Ho
Career Development	0.176	0.205	0.177	0.857	0.394	Accept Ho
Social Personal Development	0.639	0.103	0.659	6.186	0.000	Reject Ho

Dependent Variable: Values Formation of Intermediate Learners
R= 0.75, R2=0.5625, F-ratio=42.725, p-value= .000

Regression coefficients reveal that not all domains of contextualized school guidance activities significantly influence the values formation of intermediate learners. Among the three domains, only Social and Personal Development had a significant impact, as indicated by its standardized coefficient ($= 0.639$) and a p-value of $.000$, which is below the $.05$ significance level.

This result led to the rejection of the null hypothesis for this domain. In contrast, Academic Development ($p = .977$) and Career Development ($p = .394$) did not show significant effects, suggesting that these areas do not directly contribute to values formation in a statistically meaningful way.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aimed to determine the level of implementation of contextualized school guidance activities in terms of: academic development, career development, and social personal development. Moreover, to determine the level of values formation of intermediate learners in terms of: courtesy rules, friendship, being family, rules of conduct in social environments, effective usage of time health and blessings, avoiding of violence and healthy living. This was followed by a discussion about the correlation between the two variables. The end part addressed which domains of contextualized school guidance activities significantly influenced values formation of intermediate learners in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur. The following are the

significant findings:

4.1. Findings—On the level of implementation of contextualized school guidance activities in terms of academic development, career development, and social personal development revealed that the always consistent implementation of contextualized school guidance activities across academic, career, and personal-social development, all of which were rated very extensive. Career development received the highest rating, while both the academic development and social personal development had the lowest, though still categorized as very extensive. This highlights the effectiveness of school guidance programs in addressing various student needs, reinforcing the importance of sustaining and enhancing these initiatives for continued student growth and success.

On the the values formation of intermediate learners in terms of courtesy rules, friendship, being family, rules of conduct in social environments, effective usage of time health and blessings, avoiding of violence and healthy living: The findings highlight the strong values formation of intermediate learners, with very extensive ratings across various aspects, including courtesy, friendship, family relationships, social conduct, time management, and healthy living. Friendship emerged as the most strongly manifested value, while avoiding violence received the lowest rating, indicating a need for further reinforcement in conflict resolution and nonviolent behavior.

Clearly, the findings inferred a strong significant relationship between the Implementation of contextualized school guidance activities

and values formation of intermediate learners in Padada District, Division of Davao del Sur. Consequently, it is anticipated that improving contextualized school guidance activities will enhance values formation of intermediate learners, thereby positively influencing the overall classroom learning atmosphere.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the regression analysis, Regression coefficients reveal that not all domains of contextualized school guidance activities significantly influence the values formation of intermediate learners. Among the three domains, only Social and Personal Development had a significant impact. This result led to the rejection of the null hypothesis for this domain. In contrast, Academic Development and Career Development did not show significant effects, suggesting that these areas do not directly contribute to values formation in a statistically meaningful way.

4.3. Recommendations—Given the analysis above and the implications it may have, recommendations include DepEd creating policies to integrate values like empathy and emotional regulation into guidance programs. Counselors should receive training in social-emotional learning and conflict resolution. School heads should improve guidance activities with workshops and peer mentoring, collaborating with local professionals. Teachers should integrate values into lessons and foster a safe, supportive classroom. Students should engage in self-reflection and peer support initiatives. Future research should explore factors like culture and digital engagement to inform more targeted, culturally relevant guidance interventions.

5. References

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